

Evaluation of mutation rates in Nigerian father-son pairs using Y-STR markers

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Abstract

Male-specific Y-STR markers are a valuable complement to autosomal STR testing, especially in sexual assault cases, but mutation rates can affect interpretations and require careful evaluation. The Yfiler™ Plus PCR Amplification Kit, containing 27 Y-STR loci, including 7 rapidly mutating loci (mutation rates $> 1 \times 10^{-2}$), was assessed using Nigerian samples. Buccal swabs from 148 father-son pairs underwent DNA extraction with the QIAamp® DNA Mini Kit. Paternity was confirmed using the VeriFiler™ Express PCR Amplification Kit with a Combined Paternity Index threshold of 10,000. All 148 pairs showed no paternity mismatches. Y-STR profiles were generated with the Yfiler™ Plus kit, and mutation rates with binomial 95% confidence interval (CI) were calculated. Results were compared with mutation rates from the Y Chromosome Haplotype Reference Database (YHRD). A total of 29 one-step mutations were identified across 15 markers, with the highest mutation rates at DYS518 (0.0338, 95% CI: 0.0111-0.0771), DYS458, and DYS449 (0.0270, 95% CI: 0.0074-0.0678). Approximately 48% of mutations were repeat gains, and 52% were losses. Except for three pairs with two mutations, all mutations appeared once per pair. YHRD mutation rates for DYS458 and DYS518 were lower than the 95% CI obtained in the Nigerian dataset. Additionally, the rapidly mutating markers; DYS627, DYS570, and DYF387S1 had mutation rates lower than the 0.01 rate indicated by the manufacturer. Although limited by the small sample size, this study highlights the need to expand Y-STR mutation rate evaluations and establish population-specific rates for accurate forensic and relationship testing.

Keywords

Yfiler™ Plus PCR Amplification Kit, Y-STRs, rapidly mutating markers, mutation rates, father-son pairs, population-specific genetics.

Introduction

The Y chromosome is a male lineage marker that is transmitted almost intact from father to son across generations. Variations arise through recombination with the X chromosome, which occurs only in two pseudo-autosomal regions outside of the male-specific, non-recombining region, and through mutations. Due to the high number of mitotic events in spermatogenesis, mutations between father and son are expected. However, the mutation rate has been observed to vary dependent on the population and the region of the chromosome in which the genetic marker is located [1].

The characteristics of the male-specific part of the Y chromosome, inherited as a single set of genetic markers (i.e., haplotype), make it ideal for use in various forensic scenarios. Analysis of Y-chromosome Short Tandem Repeat (Y-STR) markers, for example, can enable the identification of Y haplotypes specific to the paternal lineage of a male perpetrator in sexual assault cases. Y-STRs can also be utilised in parentage and kinship testing, as well as in identification of missing persons and mass disaster victims. Due to their high inter-population variability, Y-STRs can additionally be employed to infer biogeographical origins, which can be valuable as an investigative lead for unknown individuals and for studying historical migration patterns [2-3].

Among the commercial kits available for Y-STR typing, the Yfiler™ Plus PCR Amplification Kit contains 27 Y-STR loci, including 7 rapidly mutating loci (DYS576, DYS627, DYS518, DYS570, DYS449, and DYF387S1a/b) with mutation rates reportedly exceeding 1×10^{-2} [4-5]. This kit incorporates the original 17 loci from the Yfiler™ PCR Amplification Kit, along with an additional 10 loci, making it one of the most comprehensive options available for forensic and relationship testing involving Y-chromosome analysis.

Forensic applications of Y-STR typing require information on haplotype frequencies worldwide. To facilitate this, the Y Chromosome Haplotype Reference Database (YHRD) was established to generate frequency estimates for quantitative assessments. The database contains extensive data on different populations and also provides combined mutation rates for common Y-STRs [6]. Although the YHRD website includes a national database for Nigeria, with haplotype counts of

497 for Y17 and 358 for Y27 (Release 69), and other studies have been published on forensic parameters for Y-STRs in Nigerian populations [7-8], specific data on mutation rates for Nigerians are still lacking.

Given the impact that mutations can have on the interpretation of forensic cases and the differences observed across population, the objective of this study was to evaluate the mutation rate of Y-STRs present in the Yfiler™ Plus kit in Nigerian father-son pairs.

Material studied, methods, techniques

Study samples

After obtaining informed consent, buccal swabs were collected from 148 father-son pairs with self-declared Nigerian ethnicity.

DNA extraction and Y-STR typing

DNA was extracted using the QIAamp® DNA Mini Kit (Qiagen) and amplified with the Yfiler™ Plus *PCR Amplification Kit (Applied Biosystems™)*. The resulting profiles were manually reviewed to identify mutations within each father-son pair. These mutations were categorised into repeat gains or losses. The mutation rates were calculated by dividing the number of observed mutations for each marker by the total number of meiotic transfers observed. The binomial 95% confidence intervals (CI) of the mutation rates were calculated as previously reported [9]. The results were then compared with mutation rates reported on the YHRD website [6] (Release 69).

Confirmation of relationships

Paternity of each father-son pair was confirmed using the VeriFiler™ Express PCR Amplification Kit (*Applied Biosystems™*) [10], applying a Combined Paternity Index (CPI) threshold of 10,000.

Results

Using the results from the VeriFiler™ Express kit, paternity was confirmed for all 148 father-son pairs, with no mismatches observed. The Yfiler™ Plus Y-STRs typing results revealed a total of 29 one-step mutations across 15 markers among all

the pairs under investigation. As shown in Figure 1, eight of these loci (53%) had only one mutation, while DYS518 emerged as the locus with the highest number of mutations, followed by DYS458 and DYS449.

Figure 1: Distribution of the 29 mutations observed in the father-son pairs analysed in this study.

Overall, the mutations appeared in 26 father-son pairs. Each mutation occurred once in different pairs, except in three pairs where two mutations were observed (Figure 2a). Most of the mutations were repeat losses (52%), while the remaining 48% were repeat gains (Figure 2b).

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a)

F-S Pair	F-S Alleles	Marker	F-S Pair	F-S Alleles	Marker
A	18	DYS576	P	21	DYS570
	19			20	
B	18	DYS576	Q	17,18	DYS385
	17			16,18	
C	13	DYS389I	R	17,17	DYS385
	14			17,18	
C	30	DYS389II	S	31	DYS449
	31			32	
D	31	DYS389II	T	33	DYS449
	30			34	
E	19	DYS627	U	29	DYS449
	20			30	
F	19	DYS458	V	29	DYS393
	18			28	
G	17	DYS458	W	14	DYS393
	16			13	
H	18	DYS458	X	13	DYS439
	19			12	
D	19	DYS458	Y	14	DYS439
	18			13	
I	12	YGATAH4	H	25	DYS481
	13			24	
J	22	DYS390	Z	39,41	DYF387S1
	23			39,40	
K	42	DYS518	b) ■ Gain ■ Loss		
	43				
L	41				
	40				
M	37				
	36				
N	39				
	40				
O	40				
	41				

Figure 2: a) Alleles observed in father-son (F-S) pairs exhibiting mutations. For each pair, the father's alleles are shown at the top, and the son's alleles at the bottom. Gain mutations are highlighted in green, and loss mutations in orange. b) Pie chart representing the percentage of gain and loss mutations.

Consistent with the observations in Figure 1, the highest mutation rates were found at loci **DYS518** (0.0338, 95% CI: 0.0111-0.0771), **DYS458** and **DYS449** (0.0270, 95% CI: 0.0074-0.0678) (Table 1). When compared to the combined mutation rates reported in the YHRD database, the mutation rates for **DYS458** and **DYS518** were found to be lower than the 95% CI obtained in this study. Additionally, in this study, the rapidly mutating markers **DYS627**, **DYS570**, and **DYF387S1** exhibited mutation rates lower than the 0.01 rate indicated by the kit manufacturer.

Table 1: Mutation rate and confidence interval obtained from the study samples for each locus with mutations. The last column shows the combined mutation rates reported in the YHRD database. The loci in bold represent the rapidly mutating markers.

Yfiler™ Plus locus	Mutation rate	Binomial 95% confidence interval	YHRD mutation rate
DYS576	0.0135	0.0016-0.0480	0.0116
DYS389I	0.0068	0.0002-0.0371	0.0024
DYS389II	0.0135	0.0016-0.0480	0.0050
DYS627	0.0068	0.0002-0.0371	0.0139
DYS458	0.0270	0.0074-0.0678	0.0065
YGATAH4	0.0068	0.0002-0.0371	0.0026
DYS390	0.0068	0.0002-0.0371	0.0020
DYS518	0.0338	0.0111-0.0771	0.0106
DYS570	0.0068	0.0002-0.0371	0.0080
DYS385	0.0135	0.0016-0.0480	0.0028
DYS449	0.0270	0.0074-0.0678	0.0096
DYS393	0.0068	0.0002-0.0371	0.0013
DYS439	0.0135	0.0016-0.0480	0.0045
DYS481	0.0068	0.0002-0.0371	0.0038
DYF387S1	0.0068	0.0002-0.0371	0.0065
Overall	0.0131	0.0088-0.0187	

Discussion

Mutations can have a significant impact on the interpretation of forensic evidence. A high mutation rate, for example, can lead to false exclusions in paternity testing cases and can affect the identification of mass disaster victims [11]. For this reason, using accurate mutation rate estimates is essential to avoid misinterpretations. The present study indicates that relying on the combined Y-STRs mutation rates provided in the YHRD database may be inaccurate for the Nigerian population. In fact, some rapidly mutating markers exhibited lower mutation rates than expected, while other loci showed increased mutation rates. However, this study was limited by the small number of father-son pairs analysed, highlighting the need for further efforts to establish population-specific databases for Nigerian and other understudied populations, using larger and more diverse samples. This applies not only to Y-STR frequencies but also to mutation rates. Such databases will have significant implications for forensic casework, paternity testing, and population genetics, particularly given that mutation rates can influence the interpretation of forensic evidence.

Conclusion

The results of this study, including the lower-than-expected mutation rates for certain rapidly mutating markers and vice versa, suggest that evaluations of Y-STR mutation rates should be expanded. Additionally, the importance of establishing population-specific mutation rates is emphasised. Greater knowledge of Y-STR mutation rates would enhance the use of the Yfiler™ Plus kit, or any other Y-STR kits, in forensic and relationship testing, thereby improving accuracy and reducing the likelihood of errors.

Conflict of interest statement

All claims expressed in this article are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of their affiliated company or organisation.

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